

THE IMPORTANCE OF Gnostic SENSATION IN CHILDREN'S DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of gnostic sensations in children's development and its significance in the child's growth, alongside thoughts on the educational process and scientific perspectives of pedagogues regarding child development.

Development is a physical, psychological, and social process in a person, encompassing all innate and acquired quantitative and qualitative changes. All aspects that govern a person's behavior, including worldview, moral and aesthetic ideals, and cultural norms, are achieved through language and verbal communication. Throughout life, a person participates in the process of understanding existence. The need for knowledge is largely satisfied through language.

Another distinctive feature of humans is their unique human need—specifically, the need for communication with others, referred to as the "need for emotional communication" (K. Obukhowski). It was precisely this need that led to the emergence of language. The need for communication always leads to the acquisition of language. The reason children learn to speak is that they have to participate in activities together with adults, and for that, the child must understand what is being said to them and be able to speak themselves. Here, we can discuss the "three qualities of language" (accumulating and synthesizing experience – focusing on thought – facilitating communication) (V. A. Zvegintsev).

A.A. Leontiev, in addition to distinguishing between language and speech, also identified something present in the human mind that allows a person to use language, speak, and understand spoken words (language ability). This is the mechanism that ensures speech activity.

Typically, speech activity is divided into four parts: reading, writing, speaking, and listening. These are interconnected in pairs, and the language system is realized through two forms—oral and written.

The child's orientation toward new aspects of reality—moving from practical activity to learning about the world, then about people and their relationships—creates a need for new means of communication that serve these purposes.

The physical development of preschool children is associated with their growth in height, increase in body weight, the improvement of sensory organs, and the ability to properly control movements.

In terms of **psychological development**, significant changes occur in the formation of psychological qualities and traits within the individual during the process of cognition. **Social development** becomes evident in the child's behavior and their attitude towards the environment when they start participating in social life.

The formation of an individual is achieved through the assimilation of social and structural experience created by human society, as well as through education and upbringing. This occurs through various activities. Adults guide the child through the process of learning and mastering the content that the child needs to acquire. The content, tools, and methods of upbringing and education are explained in relation to the child's development and age. For example, when working with young children, it is taken into account that they are not yet fully adapted to independent life. As the child grows older, especially in the later preschool years, their adaptability significantly increases. Accordingly, the tasks, content, and methods of educational and upbringing activities change. By the end of the preschool period, the level of development that children reach enables the educational and upbringing work carried out with them to become more complex.

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